

Resilience and Adaptation: An In-depth Analysis of Challenges Faced by Small and Cottage Industries in Rewa District Post-COVID-19

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Abstract

This research paper aims to explore the multifaceted challenges encountered by small and cottage industries in Rewa District in the aftermath of the COVID-19 pandemic. The study will delve into the economic, social, and operational hurdles that these enterprises faced, emphasizing the unique local context of Rewa District. The research will also investigate the strategies employed by these industries to overcome the challenges and adapt to the new normal. Through a comprehensive analysis, the paper aims to provide insights into potential policy interventions and support mechanisms that can foster the resilience and growth of small and cottage industries in the post-pandemic era. Every country's economy can be supported by a thriving economy. The Industrial Revolution inspired entrepreneurial behavior. People can start a large-scale business if there is enough capital. They operate on micro, small or medium scale when resources are limited. Some of them start businesses and produce at home. These industries are called cottage industries. They produce and distribute products in a limited area.

Keywords

Small and Cottage Industries, COVID-19 Impact, Adaptation Strategies.

Introduction

Small and Cottage Industries (SCIs) form a cornerstone of economies worldwide, serving as dynamic contributors to employment, economic development, and community sustainability. These enterprises, often characterized by their modest scale, local focus, and diverse product offerings, play a pivotal role in fostering entrepreneurship, preserving traditional craftsmanship, and supporting decentralized economic growth. In contrast to large-scale industries, Small and Cottage Industries are typically characterized by their compact size, flexibility, and adaptability. These enterprises span a wide array of sectors, including manufacturing, handicrafts, agro-processing, and services. What sets them apart is their

ability to operate on a smaller scale, often within local communities, thereby ensuring a more direct and tangible impact on the socio-economic fabric of the regions they inhabit. Small and Cottage Industries are engines of employment, providing livelihoods to a significant portion of the global workforce, particularly in developing economies. They serve as incubators for innovation, allowing for the exploration of niche markets, experimentation with novel ideas, and the preservation of cultural heritage through artisanal craftsmanship. In many cases, SCIs act as catalysts for inclusive growth, offering opportunities for marginalized and underprivileged individuals to engage in economic activities and improve their quality of life.

The significance of Small and Cottage Industries extends beyond economic dimensions. These enterprises often contribute to the preservation of indigenous skills, traditional knowledge, and cultural heritage. Their decentralized nature promotes regional development, reduces urban-rural disparities, and enhances the overall resilience of local economies. Despite their numerous contributions, Small and Cottage Industries face a myriad of challenges, ranging from limited access to finance and technology to competition from larger enterprises. Moreover, the advent of global disruptions, such as the COVID-19 pandemic, has added unprecedented layers of complexity to their operational landscapes.

This exploration into the realm of Small and Cottage Industries seeks to uncover the intrinsic value they bring to economies, the challenges they navigate, and the strategies employed for sustained growth. Through a comprehensive understanding of these enterprises, we aim to shed light on the pivotal role they play in shaping the economic and social tapestry of communities, and subsequently, contribute to the formulation of policies and strategies that support their resilience and prosperity.

Housework is the mainstay of many families in India. Home businesses have the advantage that they can be started with very little investment, so this type of business is ideal for low-income earners/local residents. In addition, the raw materials required for the production of household products can be easily found in the environment. Homes and small businesses have great potential for job creation. Additionally, people working in this industry are basically self-employed. Home and small businesses account for nearly 40% of India's gross domestic product. There are approximately 3.5 million units in Madhya Pradesh, providing employment to more than 2.2 million people. Additionally, experience shows that this job provides financial independence to women in both developed and developing countries. Additionally, the involvement of the entire family in product production provides year-round employment options for many families.

Review of Literature

1. **Graham Bannock (1981)** provides a clear picture of the problems of private companies, showing how they identify larger problems in the financial system. He realized that the advent of financial dynamism inherent in small business could help create the financial reforms needed to promote free expansion.
2. **Chuta Envyng Chita and Carl Lied Holm [1985]** conducted a comprehensive study of SSIs in Sierra Leone and examined SSI efforts in terms of production, marketing and employment.
3. **Siddhartha Shankar Dash and others. [1990]** discussed the operational problems of driven SST units in a test conducted in the Balasori district of Orissa.
4. **In his research, Rama Swamy (1993)** examined three ideas related to small-scale production, specifically: small businesses use more energy per unit of capital, generate more income per unit of capital, small businesses use more efficient products than small businesses. Big companies are interested in TFV women.

Objective of the study

1. Examine the extent to which small and cottage industries in Rewa District were affected by the COVID-19 pandemic.
2. Investigate the resilience measures adopted by small and cottage industries in response to the challenges posed by COVID-19.
3. Identify specific challenges faced by these industries during and after the pandemic.

Research Methodology

A. Statement of the Problem: Even though family businesses are still small, they still have to compete with other companies, whether they are other families or large companies. This requires them to use new technologies to increase efficiency and productivity. They also have to compete for labor resources, which can become particularly difficult as countries develop and wages rise. In this case, the government announced a closure due to a new epidemic on March 25, 2020. During this period of closure, there was a decrease in business from villa apartments. Due to lack of labor and raw materials, domestic units cannot continue the production process. The results for bungalow units show that growth is not good. This study will attempt to examine the performance of home businesses during the COVID-19 pandemic.

- B. Scope of the study:** This study is used only to examine the problems faced by domestic enterprises in their businesses, especially in production, marketing, human resources, money production and sales. It also examines the strategies adopted by domestic businesses to prevent the crisis during COVID-19.
- C. Methodology:** Research methods are described below, including data collection methods, data collection tools, and sample design, statistical tools used in data analysis, research hypotheses, and research areas.
- D. Data Collection:** This study is based on primary and secondary data. Primary data was collected from 171 villa owners. Secondary data is collected from books, magazines, newspapers and encyclopaedias.
- E. Instruments used for Data Collection:** Primary data will be collected from 171 settlements using a qualitative survey and pretest. According to the search test, some redundant and unnecessary questions will be removed from the tool, while some questions will be made easier. The results of the pilot study will help researchers design the final survey collect information from respondents.
- F. Sampling Design:** There are 53 revenue villages in Rewa district. There are a total of 306 bungalows in 53 tax villages. Rao calculator is used to determine size. The population of 306 people was entered into Rao's calculator. The sample size with 95% significance was determined as 171 business units. A simple sampling technique will be used in this research to collect primary data from 171 homeowners.
- G. Statistical Tools Used for Data Analysis:** Percentage analysis was used to analyze word frequency. A case study was used to identify the strategies adopted by the domestic sector to cope with the COVID-19 crisis.

Data Analysis and Interpretation

This chapter presents the job profile of housework, the problems faced by housework during COVID-19 and the strategies adopted to solve the problem during COVID-19. Issues with organization products during COVID-19. Job Profile for Cottage Industry. This section includes the business profile, for example, how many years the business has been operating and the products it produces. Table 1 shows the business profile of the domestic enterprise.

Table-1.1: Business Profile of the Cottage Industries

Business Profile		No of Respondent	%
Year of running the business	Below – 10	58	33.92
	05 – 10	71	41.52
	Above – 10	42	24.56

Source: Primary Data

Table-1.2: Business Profile of the Cottage Industries

Business Profile		No of Respondent	%
Product Produced	Honey Candy	13	7.60
	Snacks	20	11.70
	Pickles	22	12.87
	Masala Powder	12	7.02
	Temple Ghee Lamps	24	14.04
	Dry Fish Packets	6	3.51
	Papad	18	10.53
	Parotta	16	9.36
	Home Made Jaggery Sweets	19	11.11
	Soap Oil	21	12.28

Source: Primary Data

Interpretation: Out of the 171 businesses, 71 (41.52%) have been operating for 5-10 years, 58 (33.92%) have been in operation for less than 5 years, and 42 (24.56%) have been in operation for more than 10 years. Of the 171 enterprises, 24 (14.04%) are butter, 22 (12.87%) are confectionery, 21 (12.28%) are soap, 20 (11.7%) are mouth production, 19 (11.11%) were producing at home. jaggery, 18 (10.53%) cake, 16 (9.36%) parota, 13 (7.6%) sweet honey, 12 (7.02%) masala powder, 6 (3.51%) was filled with dried fishes.

Problems Faced by Cottage Industries during COVID-19

In this section, five problems such as production, marketing, finance, human resources and inventory problems faced by cottage industries during COVID-19 are studied.

- 1. Production Problems Faced by Cottage Industries during COVID-19:** Efficiency is the key to productivity. Production is a combination of many things; people, money, materials and machines. When the right materials are available at the right time, in quantity and quality, production runs smoothly. Some units use machines for production, while others use machines for packaging. Table-2 shows the production problems faced by taxis during the emergence of the new virus (COVID-19).

Table-2: Production Problems Faced by Cottage Industries during COVID-19

Production Problems	No. of Respondent	%
Perishable nature of goods	21	12.28
Lack of storage facilities	81	47.37
Price fluctuation of inventories	69	40.38
Total	171	100

Source: Primary Data

Interpretation: Out of the 171 enterprises, 92 (53.8%) faced the problem of using the existing production process, 52 (30.41%) faced the problem of insufficient capacity, and 27 (15.79%) faced the problem of lack of knowledge about modern production. information.

2. Marketing Problems Faced by Cottage Industries during COVID-19: Businesses give life to the products created by companies. It helps promote the product and encourages people to buy again and again. Table-3 shows the economic problems faced by households in the country during the outbreak of the new virus (COVID-19).

Table-3: Marketing Problems Faced by Cottage Industries during COVID-19

Marketing Problems	No. of Respondent	%
Unable to cover wider area	60	35.09
Lack of advertising opportunities	40	23.39
Rapidly changing marketing mix	71	41.52
Total	171	100

Source: Primary Data

Interpretation: 71 out of 171 businesses (41.52%) faced the problem of rapid business change, 60 (35.09%) faced the problem of not being able to cover the business, and 40 (23.39%) faced the problem of lack of advertising.

3. Human Resources Problems Faced by Cottage Industries during COVID-19: Human resources are the most important part of a business's products. It helps promote the product and encourages people to buy again and again. Table-4 shows the economic problems faced by households in the country during the outbreak of the new virus (COVID-19).

Table-4: Human Resources Problems Faced by Cottage Industries during COVID-19

Human Resource Problems	No. of Respondent	%
Lack of human resources	79	46.20
Demand for high remuneration	39	22.81
Turnover/Absence of human resources	53	30.99
Total	171	100

Source: Primary Data

Interpretation: Out of 171 businesses, 79 (46.2%) faced the problem of lack of human capital, 53 (30.99%) faced the problem of turnover/understaffing, and 39 (22.81%) faced the problem of yes. To be careful.

4. Finance Problems Faced by Cottage Industries during COVID-19: Finance is considered the lifeblood of business. If a company encounters problems with location, implementation and distribution, it will affect the development of the business. Table-5 describes the financial challenges faced by the local economy during COVID-19.

Table-5: Finance Problems Faced by Cottage Industries during COVID-19

Finance Problems	No. of Respondent	%
Shortage of funds	79	46.20
Limited sources of money borrowing	39	22.81
High rate of interest	53	30.99
Total	171	100

Source: Primary Data

Interpretation: Of the 171 businesses, 79 (46.2%) face the problem of insufficient funds, 39 (22.81%) face the problem of low capital, and 53 (30.99%) face the problem of borrowing at high interest rates.

5. Inventory Problems Faced by Cottage Industries during COVID-19: Products sold as lubricants for commercial use. Products include raw materials, labor, finished products, scrap, etc. takes place. Table-6 shows the supply problems experienced by the domestic industry during the COVID-19 period.

Table-6: Inventory Problems Faced by Cottage Industries during COVID-19

Finance Problems	No. of Respondent	%
Perishable nature of goods	21	12.28
Lack of storage facilities	81	47.37
Price fluctuation of inventories	69	40.35
Total	171	100

Source: Primary Data

Interpretation: 81 out of 171 businesses (47.37%) faced the problem of insufficient storage space, 69 (40.35%) faced the problem of price fluctuation in stocks, and 21 (12.28%) faced the problem of damaged goods.

Table-7: Present Situation of the Cottage Industries

Situation of the company	%
Profitable	25.6%
Natural	57.7%
Loss	16.7%

Source: Primary Data

Interpretation: Currently, 25.6% of these companies are profitable companies and are still making profits. 57.7% of the companies are medium-sized, meaning the company does not do any business. Finally, 16.7% of companies will lose money. That's why they need to have a plan for every situation.

Table-8: Expected time for the Cottage Industries recovery

Situation of the company	%
Within 1 month	28.2%
Within 6 month	53.8%
Within 1 year	10.3%
More than 1 year	7.7%

Source: Primary Data

Interpretation: Small businesses are in a difficult situation due to the Covid-19 outbreak. Therefore, there needs to be some time to recover, 28.2% of 78 companies need 1 month to recover, 53.8% need 6 months to recover, 10.3% need 1 year, 7.7%. Others want to recover. Companies need 1 year back. It will take more than a year for the business to recover.

Suggestions

On the basis of findings of the study, some suggestions are offered.

As we move from a COVID-19 health crisis to an economic crisis, we are trying to imagine how private businesses everywhere will face this crisis and where we should focus our efforts. The outbreak of the novel coronavirus (COVID-19) has caused a global health and financial crisis. Communication, business, growth and business are all intertwined. The emergency will impact the GDP growth of the Indian economy by around 1-2% by the end of 2020. The biggest victims will be the private sector and the poor. This bleak forecast shows no deception but a real opportunity. India is not a big country.

1. The central government, through banks, has announced various schemes to benefit the domestic economy during COVID-19 to emerge from the financial crisis. Therefore, rural areas need to turn to banks to collect and use health information.
2. When people do not have enough resources due to the lockdown, home businesses are forced to use family members for their work.
3. To avoid losses from price fluctuations, companies must sell their products on a first-in, first-out basis.
4. They can deliver on time door to door for government transportation.
5. They have to buy raw materials in bulk to get discounts and have raw materials.

Conclusion

Depression, troubles and problems are an inevitable part of life. In this way, the company faced many problems. Now this struggle is happening due to the global epidemic Covid 19. This behavior will change when people's lives and businesses are in trouble. In order to prevent economic problems, companies, especially families, need to change their strategies. They need to adjust their products and marketing mix to recoup their losses. The right ideas and effectiveness of ideas coming from household chores will change their business lives.

The study also highlights the impact of COVID-19 on small businesses and supply chains. COVID-19 has impacted cottage industries and their supply chains. COVID-19 is having a huge impact on our supply chain and bringing it together every day. This research can be extended by using a multi-model dynamic approach to evaluate issues. The relationship between boundaries can be related to the outcome of the description itself.

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About the Author

¹**Mahima Shukla** is a seasoned research scholar delving into the impact of household and cottage industries on socio-economic development, with a special focus on Satna district. With a rich background in education and geography, she holds master's degrees in both fields, enabling her to bring a multidisciplinary perspective to her research, with over 13 years of teaching experience, Mahima possesses a deep understanding of educational dynamics and geographical contexts, which enhances her ability to analyze the socio-economic landscape effectively. Her research aims to shed light on the crucial role of small-scale industries in fostering local development and prosperity.

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